

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies: El Salvador

Version 1

**International
Science Council**

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About the World Data System:

Founded in 2008, the [World Data System](#) (WDS) is an affiliated body of the International Science Council (ISC). Its mission is to enhance the capabilities, impact, and sustainability of its member repositories and data services by fostering trusted communities of scientific data repositories. The WDS also aims to strengthen the entire lifecycle of data management, ensuring that high-quality data supports first-class research output. Additionally, it advocates for accessible data along with transparent and reproducible science.

About the WDS series on Scientific Data Repository-related Policies:

The World Data System (WDS) Policy Series reviews country-specific policies related to the governance of scientific data repositories at the national level. Documenting these policies comprehensively is critical to fostering global collaborations and advancing science for the common good.

To this end, WDS is committed to maintaining and continually updating a list of national Open Science policies pertaining to data repositories. Additionally, WDS will host periodic webinars featuring experts from multiple countries to discuss their unique perspectives on Open Science Policies and how they impact data repositories. These sessions aim to inform researchers and policymakers on how to navigate international policy landscapes effectively.

In developing this Open Science Policy Series, WDS's goal is to create avenues for sharing knowledge and enhancing global scientific collaboration efforts. Ultimately, we hope this approach will promote transparency and ensure that science continues to work towards the common good by leveraging diverse international expertise. Note that the papers in this series will continually be updated with new and emerging information as it becomes available. The World Data System welcomes your input on these documents, including textual updates, references, policy suggestions, and link corrections, by emailing wds-ipo@utk.edu.

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Acronyms

OD	Open Data
OA	Open Access
NODP (PNDA)	National Open Data Policy (Política Nacional de Datos Abiertos)
PAIL (LAIP)	Public Access to Information Law (Ley de Acceso a Información Pública)
(NEOD) ENDA	National Ecosystem of Open Data (Ecosistema Nacional de Datos Abiertos)
ICOD (CIDA)	Institutional Committee on Open Data (Comité Institucional de Datos Abiertos)
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable y Reusable
WDS	World Data System

Introduction

The open data policy promoted by the Presidency of the Republic of El Salvador establishes a set of guidelines that conform with the World Data System's (WDS) data requirements and users' needs in the academic environment.

The National Open Data Policy (NODP) identifies the data produced by an entity and determines possible publication exceptions abiding by the Public Access to Information Law (PAIL). This verified data will form and integrate the institutional data inventory, which makes the Government Open Data Catalog.

There is a need for an open data policy instrument according to FAIR principles, linking data to academia and the country's scientific and technological development. Additionally, there is a statement from the Government of El Salvador that commits to open access to data generated by state institutions.

Note that the papers in this series will continually be updated with new and emerging information as it becomes available. The World Data System welcomes your input on these documents, including textual updates, references, policy suggestions, and link corrections, by emailing wds-ipo@utk.edu.

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies

Scientific data repository-related policies specific to El Salvador include:

- National Open Data Policy

Background: The present National Open Data Policy (NODP) mandates the proactive release of data that enables the generation of information within institutions. This serves as a fundamental complement to the Public Access to Information Law (PAIL), which, since its enactment in 2011, has made all documentation produced in public administration available to the population. Based on these initiatives undertaken by an Open Government, it is evident that this government recognizes the importance of opening data to foster more effective public policies and to integrate various sectors of society in the collaborative formulation of solutions to civic issues.

This approach leverages communication technologies to promote knowledge, modernization, and public participation in governance.

- Statement on Transparency and Open Data

The President's Secretary of Innovation provides a statement regarding open data, the use of information technologies, and the transparency of data generated from public funds.

- El Salvador's Digital Agenda

Aspects of the agenda related to open data:

Transparency and Open Data: Support and standardize the generation of datasets in open formats for public use, as well as the publication of official information across all state institutions.

Launch of a digital public library program to provide access to scientific information, public data in open formats, and more. This program will be integrated with university libraries as well as national and international organizations.

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